

Description of the sixth known species from the genus *Nanopsocus* Pearman, 1928 (Insecta: Psocodea) from Zanzibar

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Abstract: This study describes a new species, *Nanopsocus ajabu* n. sp., discovered on Unguja Island, Zanzibar. The species exhibits unique morphological characteristics and complex colour patterns. Material was collected and examined following standard protocols, with specimen deposited at the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, Bulgaria. An identification key for all known *Nanopsocus* species is provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, equatorial Africa, identification, insects, new species

Introduction

The understanding of Psocodea fauna in equatorial Africa remains limited, with recent efforts focusing on exploration in Zanzibar, Kenya, and Uganda (Georgiev, 2021, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2024a, 2024b). However, comprehensive studies in East Africa have been scarce, leaving significant gaps in our knowledge of psocid species diversity, particularly in understudied regions along the east coast and island areas. The genus *Nanopsocus* Pearman, 1928 is comprised of five known species mostly associated with coastal habitats. In this short paper I describe a sixth species of this genus from the Unguja Island, Zanzibar. In addition a simple identification key is proposed for all known *Nanopsocus* species.

Material and methods

Psocoptera specimens were collected from Unguja Island, Zanzibar, Tanzania, between 3–9 March 2024. The specimens were preserved in 96% ethanol. Photographs of the specimens in glycerin were captured using a Canon PowerShot SX500IS camera through

the eyepiece of an Optika light microscope. The collected material has been deposited at the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, Bulgaria (NMNHS). The identification of species in this paper is based on original descriptions (Pearman, 1928; Badonnel, 1969, 1976, 1977; Baz, 1990), and measurements were conducted following the methodology outlined by Lienhard (1998). Species distribution is according Lienhard (2016).

Measurements abbreviations: LC – body length; F+tr – hind femur and trochanter length; T – hind tibia length; t1, t2, t3 – tarsomeres of hindtarsus (lengths measured from condyle to condyle); FW – forewing; HW – hindwing; D – anteroposterior diameter of the compound eye; IO – shortest distance between compound eyes.

Results and discussion

Family Tapinellidae Enderlein, 1908
Genus *Nanopsocus* Pearman, 1928

Vertex not extended upwards into processes. Claws of each pair different, one claw foliaceous, the other normal (Smithers, 1990) (Fig. 2A).

Fig. 1. Habitat view of the type locality of *Nanopsocus ajabu* n. sp., along with the sampled dry branches with leaves of various bushes, indicated by arrows.

Nanopsocus ajabu n. sp.

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Material examined: Holotype: BG-NMNHS-ENT-000000006219, 1 ♀, Zanzibar, Unguja Island, Uroa Village, S6° 05' 29.0" E039° 24' 53.9", 4 m a.s.l., plantations mixed with various bushes, from dry branches with leaves of bushes (Fig. 1), 6.03.2024, collected by beating the vegetation, National Museum of Natural History (NMNHS).

Type locality: Tanzania, Zanzibar, Unguja Island, Uroa Village, S6° 05' 29.0" E039° 24' 53.9", 4 m a.s.l., plantations mixed with various bushes.

Description (after 15 days in 96% ethanol): Freshly imagnated female: Colouration: The species is creamy-white with a complex dark brown pattern, particularly noticeable on the head (Fig. 2B). There are asymmetrical spots and bands on both sides (Fig. 2C). A brown band of irregular spots extends from the postcypeus to the paraprocts, including along the lateral side of the abdomen, with another such band present below it. The dorsal abdominal area displays

transverse bands along each tergite, while the ventral area appears pale and whitish. The compound eyes are greyish-blue with a light brown band in the middle (Fig. 2D), while the ocelli are pale, surrounded by reddish-brown pigment (Fig. 2C). The palps are pale, except for one brown band in the middle of P4. Both antennae and legs exhibit a grey-brownish coloration. The forewings are blackish-grey, transparent, with a pale band along CuP, while the hind wings are paler, with two pale bands along A and CuP (Fig. 2E, F).

Morphology: This species is small, with a body length (LC) of 1.0 mm. It is macropterous, with well-developed wings, the forewing almost as long as the body. Venation follows the pattern depicted in Fig. 2. The hind wings are slender and narrow. The lacinia bears two closely situated cusps, with the outer one slightly longer (Fig. 2G). Claws are typical for the genus, being asymmetrical. The antennae do not reach the abdominal apex. The legs are relatively long, with t1 notably longer than t2 and t3, which are of equal length. Gonapophyses typical for the genus display delicate dorsal valves, much less developed than the external valves. The T-sclerite remains unknown, possibly due to its invisibility, potentially owing to the poorly chitinised body of the specimen.

Fig. 2. *Nanopsocus ajabu* n. sp. (holotype, female): A – asymmetrical claws, characteristic for the genus, B – side view of the specimen, C – dorsal side of the head, D – lateral side of the head with focus on the compound eye, E – forewing, F – hind wing, G – lacinia, H – lateral side of the abdominal apex with focus on the ciliation (A, G, H – not to scales).

The epiproct and paraprocts are rounded, adorned with long setae (Fig. 2H).

Measurements (in mm): Holotype (female): LC = 1.00; F+tr = 0.48; T = 0.45; t1 = 0.25, t2, t3 = 0.06, FW = 0.82, HW = 0.66, D = 0.12, IO = 0.27, IO/D = 2.25.

Male: Unknown.

Diagnosis: In terms of body coloration, *N. ajabu* n. sp. displays a striking difference from all known species within the genus. Additionally, its lacinia possesses the most closely situated cusps among the genus. While its head pattern bears a resemblance to that of *Tapinella picta* Badonnel, 1986 from Mexico, as depicted in Badonnel’s drawings (1986), it is not identical, featuring some additional spots. It is noteworthy, however, that these two species belong to different genera, a distinction clearly delineated by their claw morphology.

Etymology: The species is named “*ajabu*,” meaning “wonderful” in Swahili, in reference to its intricate and beautiful body pattern.

Habitat: The species was collected from dry leaves of coastal xeric bushes on coral limestone terrains.

The discovery of *Nanopsocus ajabu* n. sp. on Unjuja Island, Zanzibar, expands our understanding of psocid diversity in equatorial Africa, particularly in understudied coastal regions. The unique morpholog-

ical features and intricate colour patterns of this species underscore the need for further exploration and documentation of insect biodiversity in similar habitats. Additionally, the proposed identification key provides a valuable tool for researchers to distinguish between known *Nanopsocus* species (see below). Continued efforts in biodiversity research, coupled with habitat conservation measures, are crucial for preserving and understanding the rich insect fauna of equatorial ecosystems.

Identification key to all known species from the genus *Nanopsocus*

1. Apterous 2
 - Macropterous or brachypterous 3
2. Antennae about twice as long as body length
 - ... *N. longicornis* Badonnel, 1976 (Madagascar)
 - Antennae shorter
 - *N. falsus* Badonnel, 1977 (Angola)
3. Head with complex pattern of stripes and elongated spots *N. ajabu* n. sp.
 - Head unicolour 4
4. Forewings unicolour, grey-brownish
 - *N. oceanicus* Pearman, 1928 (widely distributed)
 - Forewings with dark and light spots 5

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6. Brachypterous, forewings with relatively pointed apex, T-sclerite with long arms
..... *N. trifasciatus* (Badonnel, 1969)
(Angola, Uganda)
— Macropterous, forewings typical for the genus, T-sclerite with short arms
..... *N. pictus* Baz, 1990 (Equatorial Guinea)

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